

A Comparative Study of Ego Strength and Anxiety between Government and Private School Students of Ranchi Town

Ashok Malhotra^{1*}

¹Ph.D. Research Scholar University
Department of Psychology, Ranchi University, Ranchi

Dr. Sushmita Kumari²

²Guest Lecturer, J.J College Jhumari Telaiya,
Koderma, Jharkhand

Surbhi³

³Ph.D. Research Scholar University
Department of Psychology, Vinoba Bhave University, Hazaribag

Abstract:- The main purpose of this research was to find out the mean difference of Ego Strength and Anxiety between Government and Private school students. The total of 160 school students belonging to Government and Private school, were taken. The research tool for ego strength was measured by Hasan's ego strength scale, and a tool for anxiety was made by Durganand Sinha. t-test was applied to check the significant differences of ego strength and anxiety between Government and Private school students. To check the relationship between ego strength and anxiety, the Pearson correlation method is used. The study revealed that there was a significant difference between Government and Private school students in ego strength and anxiety. The positive correlation between ego strength and anxiety among school students.

Keywords:- Ego strength and anxiety

I. INTRODUCTION

In Sigmund Freud's psychoanalytic theory of personality, ego strength is the ability of the ego to deal effectively with the demands of the Id, the superego and reality. Those with little ego strength may feel torn between these competing demands while those with too much ego strength can become too unyielding and rigid. Ego strength helps us maintain emotional stability and cope with internal and external stress. According to Freud, personality is composed of three elements: the id, the Ego and the Super ego. The Id is made up of all the primal urges and desires and is the only part of personality present at birth. The super-ego is the part of personality that is composed of the internalized standards and rules that we acquire from our parents and society. It is the part of personality that pressures people to behave morally. Finally, the ego is the component of personality that mediates between the demands of reality, the urges of the id and the idealistic, but often unrealistic, standards of the super-ego.

An understanding of the concept of ego strength depends on an understanding of the ego's functions because, "We are used to judging the strength of the ego on the basis of its behavior in typical situations (Hartmann, 1964)." Ego strength, according to Sigmund Freud's psychoanalytic theory of personality, is the ego's capacity to successfully deal with the demands of the Id, the superego, and reality. People with weak egos could feel conflicted by these conflicting expectations, while people with strong egos might become excessively inflexible and uncompromising. Ego strength aids in emotional stability and stress management both internally and externally. The id, the Ego, and the Super-ego are the three components that make up personality, according to Sigmund Freud. The Id is the only aspect of personality that is present from birth and is composed of all fundamental wants and desires.

According to Erikson (1964), ego strength refers to the attributes that "human beings steer themselves and others through life." Strengths were identified as the results of effective stage resolutions in Erikson's psychosocial stage theory (Erikson 1964). The frequency of participation in religious activities and the degree of importance respondents accorded to religion are two components of faith development.

Understudied elements of Erikson's more comprehensive psychosocial theory of human development are the ego strengths. The lack of scientific discussion on this subject is notable since, in theory, ego strengths should show that psychological stage conflicts have been successfully resolved. Competence arises from industry as opposed to inferiority during latency; fidelity arises from identity as opposed to identity confusion in adolescence; love arises from intimacy as opposed to isolation in young adulthood; care arises from generativity as opposed to stagnation in middle adulthood; and wisdom arises from integrity as opposed to despair in later adulthood. The ego strengths are believed to be sequential, invariant, and hierarchical, just as the psychological stages.

In the dynamics of human behaviour, anxiety holds a central place since it is a typical response to frustration. Since worry is one of the most distressing psychic states that the human organism must deal with, it needs some form of adjustment that will provide relief. Human adjustment is heavily influenced by strategies for reducing or avoiding anxiety. Anxiety is the catalyst for a great deal of the ensuing modifications, emerging from a variety of frustrating circumstances.

In terms of behaviour, Sarason (1980) defined anxiety as a learnt or inherited response to a perceived hazardous input. According to Benjamin (1987), anxiety can interfere with focus, learning, and testing. It is not a novel notion that a student's capacity to demonstrate what they have learnt may be affected by their level of fear. Additionally, anxiety can affect learning because nervous students find it harder to focus on important elements and are more likely to be sidetracked by unimportant or incidental components of the work at hand.

Anxiety is characterized as mental suffering related to an impending setback. In this respect, it should be separated from the aggressive or fearful reactions to danger or the immediate response to dissatisfaction itself. Whatever the source of the frustration, it is understood to be hazardous since it will either create suffering or cause loss.

The degree to which the person is personally exposed to the threat also influences how anxious they are. While anxiety is always there, it is not as strong as it is when the person's life or safety is in danger. Examples of expected dangers include being bitten by a bug, having a cat scratch one's skin, or losing one's hat on a windy day. In this case as well, the hazard that raises the most concern may not even be one that poses a threat to physical safety. When a person feels that his or her existence in the group or personal sufficiency is in danger, they experience the most intense worry. Types of anxiety disorders: -Generalized anxiety disorders, Panic disorders, Phobias, Obsessive-compulsive disorders, Post-traumatic stress disorders, and Understanding anxiety disorders.

Nadeem and et al. (2012), Impact of Anxiety on Academic Achievement of University Students with Diverse Mental Capabilities in Bahawalpur (Southern Punjab), Pakistan. The findings demonstrate that both male and female pupils' academic achievement declines when anxiety levels rise. The data show that anxiety affects female students more than male students, which is notable. Worden and Sobel (2012). Ego strength and psychosocial adaptation to cancer patient. Results showed that psychosocial adaptation to cancer was related to a patient's ego strength. As correlated positively with a patient's use of effective coping strategies.

Chatterjee and Walsh (2010). Anxiety among high school students in India: Comparisons across gender, school type, social strata and perceptions of quality time with parents. Results show that anxiety was prevalent in the sample with 20.1% of boys and 17.9% of girls found to be

suffering from high anxiety. More boys were anxious than girls. Adolescents from Bengali medium schools were more anxious than adolescents from English medium schools. Shepherd and Edelman. (2009), The interrelationship of social anxiety with anxiety, depression, locus of control, ways of coping and ego strength amongst university students. There were high scores of social anxiety which were related to high scores on measures of anxiety and depression, low ego strength, external locus of control and emotion coping rather than problem-focused coping.

➤ Objectives

The main objectives of study were as under

- To study the mean scores of Ego-strength of Government and Private school students.
- To study the mean scores of Anxiety of Government and Private school students.
- To study the correlation between Ego-strength and Anxiety of school students.

➤ Hypotheses

- There is no significant difference in mean scores of Ego-strength of Government and Private school students.
- There is no significant difference in mean scores of Anxiety of Government and Private school students.
- There is no significant correlation between Ego-strength and Anxiety of school students.

II. METHOD

Participants according to the purpose of present study total 160 sample has been selected. There were 80 Government and 80 Private school students were taken as a sample from different schools in Ranchi town.

➤ Research design

The aim of present study was to study of ego strength and anxiety among Government and Private school students. For these total 160 Government and Private school students were taken as a sample. Quasi experimental design was used. To check difference between independent groups t-test was used and to study the significance correlation, Pearson correlation method was used.

➤ Tools

For this purpose, the following test tools were considered with their reliability, validity and objectivity mentioned in their respective manuals in present study two inventories were used.

➤ Hasan's Ego-Strength Scale:

Ego-strength Scale Indian adaptation of Barron's Ego Strength Scale by Q. Hasan (1974) was used to measure ego-strength of the sample of present research. The ego-strength comprised of 32 items with the two alternative response categories. The frequency of negative responses on the ego-strength scale indicates the degree of the Ego strength. The odd even reliability of the adopted scale is found to be 0.78 (corrected). The test retest reliabilities of

the adopted scale were found to be 0.86 and 0.82 respectively. The validity this scale was also found to be highly satisfactory. The analysis of the data was made by t-test.

➤ *Sinha's Anxiety Scale:*

Sinha Anxiety Scale11: It is also a self-administered test consisting of 100 Yes/ No statements. The possible score ranges from 0-100. The total score is indicative of anxiety measure of the subject. High scores indicate high level of anxiety. The split half reliability has been found to be 0.92 and validity 0.72 with Taylor's scale.

➤ *Procedure:*

According to purpose of present study for data collection the investigator explained the purpose the study to the subjects for these total 80Government and 80Private school students were taken as a sample from different part of Ranchi (Jharkhand). Testing was done personally with Government and Private school students. The whole procedure of fill the inventory was explained tot hem fully and clearly. The instructions given on questionnaire were explained to them. It was also made clear to them that these scores would be kept secret. It was checked that none of the participants left any questions unanswered or that no participants encircled both the answer given against questions

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The main objectives of present study were to study the mean scores of Ego-strength of Government and Private school students and to study the mean scores of Anxiety of Government and Private school students” In it statistical t-test method is used. To check correlation between ego strength and anxiety Karl Persian „r“ method is used. Result discussion of present study is as under the following tables and figures

Table 1 School-wise M, SD, n and t-value of Ego-strength among school students

Location	n	Mean	SD	df	Mean difference	t-value
Government	80	8.36	3.01	98	3.5	3.95**
Private	80	11.86	4.28			

**= significant at 0.01 level

Fig 1 Mean Score of Ego-Strength Among Government and Private School Students

The table-1 indicates that the mean score of ego strength in government students are 8.36 and private students are 11.86. The standard deviations for both government and private students are 3.01 and 4.28 respectively. The difference between the set was significant at 0.01 level of confidence as the value of t-test is 3.95. Findings shown that Private school students are more affected by ego strength in comparison to Government students. Private school students find themselves under more ego strength because of their multiple roles and regulations. So the first hypothesis is rejected.

Shepherd and Edelman (2009) provided evidence for their research findings, conducting a study in the High levels of social anxiety were associated with high levels of anxiety and depression, with low levels of ego strength, an external locus of control, and emotion-focused coping as opposed to problem-focused coping. The outcome matched the current study. Therefore, we can conclude that the findings presented here are supported by Shepherd and Edelman (2009) and Worden and Sobel's (2012) study.

Table 2 School-Wise M, SD, N and T-Value of Anxiety Among School Students

Location	n	Mean	SD	df	Mean difference	t-value
Government	80	34.18	8.44	98	5.67	3.01**
Private	80	39.85	10.64			

**= significant at 0.01 level

Fig 2 Mean Score of Anxiety Among Government and Private School Students

Table 2 indicates that the mean scores of anxiety in Government and Private school students are 34.18 and 39.85, and the standard deviations for both Government and Private school students are 8.44 and 10.64, respectively. The difference between these two means is significant at the 0.01 level of confidence, as the value of the t-test is 3.01. A perusal of that reveals a significant difference between the anxieties of the two groups. In this study, Private school students scored higher on anxiety in comparison to their Government school counterparts. It is not surprising because, in our culture, society gives more freedom and support to government school students. So the second hypothesis is also rejected.

Chatterjee and Walsh's (2010) research findings are supported by evidence. As a result, more guys than girls were found to be nervous. Teenagers in English-medium schools were less nervous than those in Bengali-medium schools. The outcome matched the current study. Therefore, we may state that Chatterjee and Walsh's (2010) research supports the findings of the present study.

Table 3 Correlation Coefficients Between Ego-Strength and Anxiety of School Students

Variable	Anxiety
Ego-strength	0.61**

**Significant at 0.01

From Table 3, It can be seen that the correlation coefficient between Ego-strength and Anxiety is 0.61 which is significant at 0.01 level with $df = 98$. It indicates that there is a significant positive correlation between Ego-strength and Anxiety of students. Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant correlation between Ego-strength and Anxiety of school students is rejected. Further the percentage of commonness between Ego-strength and Anxiety is 37.21%, which is moderate. It may be said that the correlation between Ego-strength and Anxiety is moderate. It means ego strength increase anxiety increase and ego strength decrease anxiety decrease among school students.

IV. CONCLUSION

There were significant differences between the mean scores of the two groups on ego strength and anxiety. Private school students are more affected by ego strength and anxiety in comparison to government students. It is not surprising because, in our culture, society renders more care, protection, and support to private school students. The correlation between ego strength and anxiety is 0.61, which is a positive correlation.

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